

Supplementary tables

Table 1. Primers used for the qPCR analysis

Target	Primer name	Primer sequence 5' -> 3'
<i>16S rRNA</i>	<i>16S_F</i> <i>16S_R</i>	TCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAG ATTACCGCGGCTGCTGG
<i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	<i>AMUC_F</i> <i>AMUC_R</i>	CAGCACGTGAAGGTGGGGAC CCTTGCGGTTGGCTTCAGAT
<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	<i>Efec_F</i> <i>Efec_R</i>	CGCTTCTTTTCCCTCCCGAGT GCCATGCGGCATAAACTG
<i>Lactobacillus murinus</i>	<i>Lan_F</i> <i>Lan_R</i>	GGCAATGATGCGTAGCCGAAC CGCACTTTTCTTCTAACAACAGG
<i>Bacteroides</i> spp.	<i>Bac sscp_F1</i> <i>Bac sscp_R1</i>	CTG AAC CAG CCA AGT AGC GT CGC AAT CGG AGT TCT TCG TG
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	<i>Sspp1_F</i> <i>Sspp1_R</i>	ATGCAAGTCGAGCGAAC(G/A)GA TGCTCAGTTCCAGTGTGGC
<i>E.coli</i>	<i>E. coli guaB_F</i> <i>E. coli guaB_R</i>	TGCTTTCCGCAGCAATGGAT CTGCGGATCAGTCACCACAC

Table 2. Data normality and statistical significance tests

Parameters	Kolmogorov–Smirnov test, P	Mann–Whitney U-test, Z	P-value	Number of animals in the total sample
Age of prolapse (autoclaved v. non-autoclaved diets) of <i>Muc2</i> ^{-/-} females	$P < 0.001$	3.71	0.0002	43
Feces from mice <i>Muc2</i>^{-/-} on autoclaved diet v. feces from mice feeding of 2 weeks non-autoclaved diet				
16S rRNA gene from <i>E. coli</i>	$P < 0.10$	2.12	0.03	7
16S rRNA gene from <i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	$P > 0.10$	0.71	0.48	7
16S rRNA gene from <i>Bacteroides</i> spp.	$P > 0.10$	0.71	0.48	7
16S rRNA gene from <i>Lactobacillus murinus</i>	$P > 0.10$	-1.41	0.16	7
16S rRNA gene from <i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	$P > 0.10$	0.35	0.72	7
16S rRNA gene from <i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	$P > 0.10$	-0.71	0.48	7
Feces from mice <i>Muc2</i>^{-/-} on autoclaved diet v. feces from mice feeding non-autoclaved diet				
16S rRNA gene from <i>E. coli</i>	$P > 0.10$	1.64	0.10	8

16S rRNA gene from <i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	$P > 0.10$	1.04	0.30	8
16S rRNA gene from <i>Bacteroides</i> spp	$P < 0.05$	2.24	0.02	8
16S rRNA gene from <i>Lactobacillus murinus</i>	$P < 0.05$	2.24	0.02	8
16S rRNA gene from <i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	$P > 0.10$	1.04	0.30	8
16S rRNA gene from <i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i>	$P > 0.10$	0.45	0.65	8
Amount of immune cells, %				
CD3+ cells in the blood of C57BL/6, %	$P > .10$	1.28	0.20	11
CD4+ cells in the blood of C57BL/6, %	$P < .01$	-2.74	0.01	11
CD8+ cells in the blood of C57BL/6, %	$P < 0.01$	2.74	0.01	11
CD19+ cells in the blood of C57BL/6, %	$P > 0.10$	-2.19	0.03	11
CD3+ cells in the blood of <i>Muc 2^{-/-}</i> , %	$P > 0.10$	0.00	1.00	9
CD4+ cells in the blood, %	$P > 0.10$	-1.72	0.09	9
CD8+ cells in the blood of <i>Muc 2^{-/-}</i> , %	$P > 0.10$	2.21	0.03	9
CD19+ cells in the blood of <i>Muc 2^{-/-}</i> , %	$P > 0.10$	1.23	0.22	9
CD3+ cells in the spleen of C57BL/6, %	$P < 0.025$	-2.61	0.01	10
CD4+ cells in the spleen of C57BL/6, %	$P > 0.10$	0.94	0.35	10
CD8+ cells in the spleen of C57BL/6, %	$P > 0.10$	0.52	0.60	10
CD19+ cells in the spleen of C57BL/6, %	$P < 0.025$	-2,61	0.01	10
CD3+ cells in the blood of <i>Muc 2^{-/-}</i> , %	$P < 0.10$	-1,57	0.12	10
CD4+ cells in the spleen of <i>Muc 2^{-/-}</i> , %	$P < 0.10$	1,98	0.05	10
CD8+ cells in the spleen of <i>Muc 2^{-/-}</i> , %	$P < 0.10$	-1,57	0.12	10
CD19+ cells in the spleen of <i>Muc 2^{-/-}</i> , %	$P < 0.10$	-1,98	0.05	10

Figure S1

A

B

C

